

GROWTH KINETICS OF IRON BORIDES BY SLURRY COATING TECHNIQUE ON XC38 STEEL

Halima. Khelifi¹, Ahmed Daas², Omar. Allaoui¹, Sami. Zidemel¹

¹Laboratory Process Engineering, university of Laghouat, B.P. 37G route de Guardia 03000 Laghouat, Algeria

E-mail : halima.khelifi@lagh-univ.dz

² University of Djelfa City 05 July Road Moudjbara P.O. Box 3117 Djelfa 17000

E-mail : ahmed.daas@univ-djelfa.dz

ABSTRACT: We can affirm that the slurry coating technique is an effective method for boriding steels, which makes it possible to obtain layers of iron boride on carbon steels practically equivalent to those produced by other techniques. It becomes very useful to carry out a study on the growth kinetics of iron boride layers produced by the slurry coating technique on XC38 steel. We carried out several treatments using three different pastes. In each paste, the activator and boring source, NaBF₄ and B₄C, are present in varying amounts. The test results made it possible to discuss the influence of the temperature, the holding time, and the proportion of the activator on the growth in the thickness of the layer formed on the treated surface.

KEYWORDS: Boriding; Kinetics; slurry coatings; activator; Activation energy Diagram contour.

1 INTRODUCTION

To ensure the long service life of mechanical parts, several techniques have been used, such as thermochemical surface hardening treatments. Therefore, the production of a very hard, wear- and corrosion-resistant surface has become one of the most important hardening operations for a wide range of mechanical construction materials to meet strict industrial requirements. Due to the technical and economic difficulties associated with the technology of carrying out the boriding treatment, several methods and techniques have been developed over the years to master and facilitate users to making a profitable and effective boriding treatment. Although there are current technologies for boriding treatments, such as powder technology, the molten salt process, or gaseous saturation, some applications, such as partial or large-part treatment, require other flexible and cost-effective processing methods. In this work, we will study the growth kinetics of iron boride using paste technology, where a light layer of slurry is applied to the surface of the substrate to be treated, and then it is entered into the furnace to form the boride layers on the surface. The material used as a substrate for the thermochemical treatments is XC38 steel. To master the boriding process with this new technique and achieve its integration on an industrial scale. In order to determine the variables that affect the kinetics of the process of forming boride layers, it is necessary to know the kinetic parameters that govern the

processing so that it becomes possible to generate the layer thickness according to certain requirements (Campos; Oseguera; Figueroa; García; Bautista; Kelemenis, 2003). The thickness of the resulting layer is related to the chemical composition of the base material and other factors such as temperature and the type of paste used. In this study, we will follow the evolution of boron diffusion in Fe₂B boride. , through the layer growth data obtained during the application of this boriding technique, the growth kinetics of the Fe₂B boride layer were analyzed by estimating its thickness as a function of the processing time in the studied temperature ranges. of the research, the objectives and the methodology. The text style is Normal, written in Times New Roman font, 11 points, justified and with a 5-mm indentation on the first line.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

The material used as a substrate for thermochemical boriding treatments in this work is XC38 steel (or C35 according to the European Standard). The carbon content of this steel is considered average between mild and hard steels.

Tableau 1. Chemical composition of steel

Eléments	C	Mn	Si	P
% wt	0.39	0.68	0.34	0.026
S	Cu	Cr	Ni	Fe
0.025	0.18	0.19	0.26	Balance

2.1 Preparation of slurry coating

slurry coatings used generally consist of two components: solid and liquid. The three compositions of coatings prepared for boriding treatments are presented in Table 2.

Tableau 2. Slurry-coating compositions

Slurry N°	B4C %	NaBF4 %	Binder
01	90	10	acetone
02	85	15	acetone
03	75	25	acetone

2.2 Preparation of slurry coating

Two steps were followed to prepare the mixture of powders with acetone. The first step concerns the mixing of boron carbide powders (B4C) with sodium fluoroborate (NaBF4) and the second step is related to the addition of acetone drops to the mixed powder until we reach a viscosity that allows us to apply the coating on the surface of the substrate with flexibility.

2.3 Preheating

To prevent swelling and flaking of the coating after the samples were introduced into the oven, we applied a preheating to a hot plate at a temperature of about 50 °C for 20 min. Figure 2.4 illustrates the preheating operation, before introduction into the furnace

2.4 Sample preparation

Sample preparation prior to thermochemical treatments is necessary to remove all contamination and ensure proper diffusion of boron over the entire surface exposed to the coating.

2.5 Boriding condition

After applying the paste to the parts, they are dried and then prepared for processing. The parts are placed in the muffle furnace, where the technological conditions of this work, such as the holding time of thermochemical treatment and the heating temperature, are indicated in the table.3

Table 3 Experimental data on the total thicknesses of the borided layers of XC38 steel

T (°C)	Activator NaBF4	Total thickness as a function of time (µm)			
		2 h	4 h	6 h	8 h
800	10 -25%	70	90	108	120
850	10- 25%	100	140	150	180
900	10- 25%	105	160	190	220
950	10- 25%	125	170	220	260

3 MEANS AND TECHNIQUES OF ANALYSIS

Microstructural analysis is a very useful examination in metallography that provides essential information on structural properties. The metallographic analysis was performed after treatments for each sample using a Leica® DMLM optical microscope and a TESCAN VEGA3 scanning electron microscope (SEM).

3.1 Model of diffusion

Temperature and time are the two most important parameters in the diffusion of boride in the processed material, since increasing one or both of the parameters causes an increase in the thickness of the layer formed during the processing process, because there is a parabolic relationship between the thickness and the time required to reach the specified thickness.). Equivalent growth constants can be deduced from experimental data on the evolution of the thickness of the layer formed as a function of temperature and time. We use the dimensional analysis of Fick's second law:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = D \frac{\partial^2 C}{\partial x^2} \quad (1)$$

Due to the presence of a relationship between processing conditions, such as temperature, time, and activation energy, we can use the Arrhenius model to express the equivalent growth constant (k).

$$K = K_0 \exp\left(-\frac{Q}{RT}\right) \quad (2)$$

In the field of thermochemistry, R is the ideal universal gas constant, while Ko is a pre-exponential component there is a relationship between the boron potential of the boron source and the substrate interface [m²s⁻¹].

The statement (3) indicates that there is a relationship between the boron content C and the diffusion coefficient D, which is constant over a distance x at a specific time t. doc, at any given time and at any given distance from the surface where diffusion occurs, the ratio or correlation between the boron content and the diffusion coefficient remains constant.as illustrated in the following equation.

$$K = \left[2\sqrt{Dt} \operatorname{erf}^{-1} \left(\frac{C_{(x,t)} - C_s}{C_0 - C_s} \right) \right]^2 \quad (3)$$

The growth parabolic constant (K) [m²s⁻¹] characterizes the diffusion process of boron in the Fe₂B layer. It is given by the equation:

$$x^2 = Kt \quad (4)$$

To estimate the activation energy (Q) required for boron diffusion in the Fe₂B layer, we use the

Arrhenius equation, which relates the diffusion coefficient to temperature. The Arrhenius equation in its logarithmic form is:

$$\ln K = \ln K_0 - \left(\frac{Q}{RT}\right) \quad (5)$$

We can estimate the activation energy required for the diffusion of the Fe₂B layer by plotting the equation in logarithm, as follows:

$$x = \sqrt{K_0 \cdot \exp\left(\frac{-Q}{RT}\right) t} \quad (6)$$

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructural analysis

The results obtained showed that boride layers were formed for the three coatings tested for a boarding treatment at 800 °C for 4 hours. However, it should be noted that the proportion of the NaBF₄ activator in the coating. affect directly on the boride layer formed on the surface of XC38 steel, which can be single-phase composed of Fe₂B borided or double-phase composed of FeB boride and Fe₂B boride. When the proportion of NaBF₄ is less than or equal to 10% the boride layer formed on the surface is only Fe₂B, while if the proportion of the activator is greater than that, the layer formed is made up of FeB and Fe₂B borides. The thickness of the total layer of FeB boride formed on the surface is found to be an increasing function with the percentage of NaBF₄ activator (Daas; Zidemel; Allaoui, 2020). The acicular teeth saw morphology is characteristic for all layers of boride formed on the surface of XC38 steel. This applies to both single-phase and two-phase layers.

Fig.1 Borided layers obtained by 15% of NaBF₄ (4 h at 800 °C)

3.2 Total Layer Thicknesses (Experimental)

The average thicknesses of the resulting boride layers as a function of the composition of the coating

and as a function of the temperature of the treatment and the duration of maintenance at this temperature are presented in Table 4.

Tableau 3. Experimental data on the total thicknesses of the borided layers of XC38 steel

T (°C)	Activator NaBF ₄	Total thickness as a function of time (µm)			
		2 h	4 h	6 h	8 h
800	10 -25%	70	90	108	120
850	10- 25%	100	140	150	180
900	10- 25%	105	160	190	220
950	10- 25%	125	170	220	260

Contour diagram

Contour diagrams are very useful in industrial applications, to quickly choose the necessary process and estimate the desired layer thickness for a particular application.

Fig.2 Diagram contour for, a) 25%, b) 15%, c) 10% of NaBF₄

A contour diagram allowed us to optimize the drilling process by the coating technology of carbon steel, showing us the experimental conditions, time and temperature according to the required layer thickness for each coating used.

3.3 Evolution of layer growth

Figure 2 represents the thickness of the boride layer as a function of temperature and processing time according to equation number 4, where we present its results and conclusions. Using the results, the growth of the layers is described using the parabolic functional equation (2). In Figure 5, the lines in this representation show a slope that corresponds to parabolic growth constants K, indicating such growth. In our case, is controlled by the diffusion of boron through the treated steel [5-6].

Figure 4 The evolution of the thickness of the bored layer as a function of temperature and processing time, according to equation 4.

3.4 Estimation of activation energy

In order to estimate the activation energy necessary for the formation of the Fe₂B boride layer on the surface of XC38 steel. Figure.5 shows the curves of Ln (k) as a function of 1/T for the boride Fe₂B formed on the surface of steel XC38 (one considers the total thickness of the borided layer formed on the surface, without distinguishing the boride FeB and Fe₂B). Applying the Arrhenius expression (Equation 2) yields the activation energy needed for the boriding process to occur, as illustrated in Figure 5. It is evident from the plot of equation (2) that the activation energy can be determined using the following formula based on the slope of the graph's resultant line:

$$Q/R = 1781.06$$

$$Q = 89.59 \text{ KJ mol}^{-1}$$

$$K_0 = 1.14 \cdot 10^{-8}$$

Table 5 illustrates that the activation energy of the boride Fe₂B produced in the coatings is nearly identical to that of the same boride produced in the

Figure 3 Graph of Ln(K) as a function of 1/T for Fe₂B molten salts when the activation energy values obtained in this work are compared with those obtained by other researchers.

Tableau 4. Values of activation energies, composition of the boriding medium, nature of the layers formed and total thickness obtained, compare to other works in the literature

Boriding Technique	Layer Nature	Thickn ess	Energy	Ref
Powders 900 °C 4 H	Fe ₂ B	90 µm	153.1	[5]
Molten Salts 950 °C 4 H	FeB + Fe ₂ B	150 µm	81.51	[1]
Slurry coating 900 °C 4 H	FeB + Fe ₂ B	136 µm	89.59 (Fe ₂ B)	This work
Slurry coating 900 °C 4 H	FeB + Fe ₂ B	160 µm	48.37 (FeB)	This work

5 CONCLUSION

In order to compare this technique with other existing techniques that are used on an industrial scale, this study allowed us to know the essence of this method as well as the conditions and steps to follow for the realization of a boriding treatment by the technique of slurry coatings on steels. The technological conditions (boriding temperature and duration of maintenance at this temperature coating composition), and the growth kinetics of boride layers and their activation energy and other parameters that can be used as evaluation criteria of this technique for boriding treatments of carbon steels

6 REFERENCE

[1] Campos, J. Oseguera, U. Figueroa, J.A. García, O. Bautista, G. Kelemenis, "Kinetic study of boron diffusion in the pasts boriding process", *Materials Science and Engineering*, 2003, Vol. 352, no(1-2), pp. 261-265.

[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-5093\(02\)00910-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0921-5093(02)00910-3)

[2] Campos Silva I, Ortiz Domínguez M, Cimenoglu H, Escobar Galindo R, Keddám M, Elias Espinosa M, López Perrusquia N. "Diffusion model for growth of Fe₂B layer pure iron", *Surface Engineering*. 2009, Vol. 27, no(3), pp.189-195.

<https://doi.org/10.1179/026708410X12550773057820>

[3] Villa Velázquez Mendoza C. Estudio del Agrietamiento Tipo Palmqvist y Evaluación de Esfuerzos Residuales en Aceros Borurados AISI 1018 [thesis]. México: Instituto Politécnico Nacional-ESIME; 2009. p. 209.

[4] Sen S, Sen U, Bindal C. The growth kinetic of borides formed on boronized AISI 4140 steel. *Vacuum*. 2005; 77(2):195-202.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.vacuum.2004.09.005>

[5] Campos-Silva I, Ortíz-Domínguez M, López Perrusquia N, Escobar-Galindo R, Gómez-Vargas OA, Hernández-Sánchez E. Determination of boron diffusion coefficients in borided tool steels. *Defect and Diffusion Forum*. 2009;283-286:681-686.

<https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/DDF.283-286.681>

[6] Sen S, Sen U, Bindal C. An approach of kinetic study of borided steels. *Surface and Coatings Technology*. 2005; 191(2-3):274-285.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.surfcoat.2004.03.040>

[7] Daas, A., Zidemel, S., Allaoui, L. A., & Allaoui, O. (2020). Paste Borided Layers Produced on XC38 Steel Using a New Activator. *Materials Performance and Characterization*, 9(3), 392-399.

DOI: 10.1520/MPC20190102